

Experimental Realization of Spontaneous Parametric Down Conversion

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ABSTRACT

Spontaneous Parametric Down-Conversion (SPDC) is a cornerstone phenomenon in nonlinear optics, where an incident high-energy photon is transformed into a pair of lower-energy photons. This quantum process serves as a fundamental tool for generating entangled photon pairs, heralded single photons, and squeezed light, making it indispensable in the realms of quantum communication, quantum computing, and precision metrology. In this paper, we present a comprehensive study on the theoretical foundations and practical realization of an SPDC experimental setup, developed for the first time at the Photonics Research Laboratory at Amirkabir University of Technology. Our setup features a self-grown potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) nonlinear crystal, illuminated by a 450 nm blue laser, to achieve parametric down-conversion into infrared photon pairs at 900 nm. By integrating a custom-designed transimpedance amplifier with a BPX65 photodiode, we have successfully amplified and detected the weak SPDC signal, demonstrating the feasibility of achieving high sensitivity with low-cost, widely available components. The experimental results align closely with theoretical predictions, showcasing the effectiveness of the system in detecting photon pairs with minimal resources. This study underscores the accessibility and scalability of SPDC technology, providing a blueprint for constructing versatile quantum optics experiments in resource-limited settings. By bridging the gap between theoretical insight and experimental realization, we aim to inspire further exploration of SPDC's potential in both foundational research and practical applications, laying the groundwork for future innovations in quantum technologies.

1 Introduction

Spontaneous Parametric Down-Conversion (SPDC)^{1,2} represents a cornerstone in the realm of nonlinear optics³ and quantum optics⁴, where a high-energy photon from a pump beam interacts with a nonlinear crystal and splits into two lower-energy photons, known as the signal and idler photons. First theoretically proposed by Klyshko in the 1960s⁵ and experimentally verified shortly thereafter, SPDC heralded a transformative era in quantum optics. Initially referred to as parametric fluorescence⁶, this phenomenon has grown into a fundamental tool, enabling the exploration of quantum entanglement⁷⁻⁹ and serving as a platform for advancing quantum technologies. From its foundational role in quantum mechanics to its practical applications in cutting-edge fields such as quantum communication¹⁰, computation¹¹, and sensing^{12,13}, SPDC exemplifies the remarkable synergy between theoretical physics and experimental realization.

One of the most remarkable features of SPDC is its intrinsic quantum mechanical nature, which facilitates the generation of entangled photon pairs and heralded single photons¹⁴. These properties are invaluable for probing the foundational principles of quantum mechanics. Groundbreaking experiments, such as tests of Bell's inequalities¹⁵ and demonstrations of quantum teleportation⁸, owe their feasibility to SPDC-based photon sources. Beyond foundational physics, the versatility of SPDC has catalyzed technological innovations in quantum key distribution¹⁶ and quantum-enhanced metrology^{17,18}, underscoring its dual role as both a scientific and engineering marvel. SPDC's ability to bridge fundamental quantum theory and real-world applications highlights its unparalleled significance in modern optics.

The adaptability of SPDC stems from its dependence on nonlinear optical properties and phase-matching conditions. Birefringent crystals, such as beta barium borate (BBO)¹⁹ and lithium niobate (LiNbO₃)²⁰, enable precise tailoring of the emitted photons' properties, including their wavelengths, polarizations, and spatial modes. This tunability allows researchers to engineer photon sources optimized for specific experimental and technological requirements, ranging from the generation of single photons to multi-photon entangled states. Such versatility has led to SPDC's adoption in diverse applications, including quantum imaging, spectroscopy, and precision measurements, where the manipulation of quantum states²¹⁻²⁶ offers profound advantages over classical techniques.

Despite its groundbreaking capabilities, SPDC faces inherent challenges, most notably its low conversion efficiency. The probability of converting a pump photon into a signal-idler pair is typically on the order of 10^{-6} to 10^{-8} , which necessitates the

use of high-power lasers and sensitive detection systems. Recent advances in photonic engineering have sought to address these limitations through innovative techniques such as quasi-phase-matched crystals, integrated photonic waveguides²⁷, and metamaterials²⁸ designed to enhance interaction efficiency. Moreover, the miniaturization of SPDC sources through integration into compact photonic circuits has opened new horizons for scalable quantum technologies²⁹. These developments promise to overcome current limitations, making SPDC a more practical tool for real-world applications^{30,31}.

In this work, we present a cost-effective implementation of an SPDC experimental setup, developed in our Photonics Research Laboratory. By utilizing a self-grown potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) crystal and a carefully designed detection system, we demonstrate the feasibility of generating and detecting entangled photon pairs with accessible components. This experimental realization underscores the accessibility of SPDC systems, paving the way for their use in resource-limited settings.

Through this study, we aim to bridge the gap between theoretical insights and experimental methodologies, providing a platform for both educational purposes and advanced research. By showcasing the potential of SPDC-based systems to inspire innovation in basic experiments in quantum optics laboratories, this work highlights the transformative impact of nonlinear optics and photonics in shaping the future of science and technology.

2 Theory

Spontaneous Parametric Down-Conversion (SPDC) is a nonlinear optical process in which a photon from a high-energy pump beam interacts with a nonlinear crystal, resulting in the generation of two lower-energy photons, referred to as the signal and idler photons. This phenomenon, governed by the principles of energy and momentum conservation, serves as a fundamental mechanism for generating entangled photons and other nonclassical light states, forming the backbone of quantum optics and numerous quantum information applications.

2.1 Nonlinear Optical Foundations

SPDC is inherently a result of the nonlinear response of a medium to intense electromagnetic fields. The polarization $\mathbf{P}$ of a nonlinear medium subjected to an electric field $\mathbf{E}$ can be expanded as:

$$\mathbf{P} = \epsilon_0 \left(\chi^{(1)} \mathbf{E} + \chi^{(2)} \mathbf{E}^2 + \chi^{(3)} \mathbf{E}^3 + \dots \right), \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, and $\chi^{(n)}$ represents the n -th order nonlinear susceptibility. SPDC is specifically facilitated by the second-order term $\chi^{(2)}$, which is present only in non-centrosymmetric materials. This term allows a high-energy photon from the pump beam to split into two lower-energy photons, satisfying the following conservation laws:

- **Energy Conservation:**

$$\hbar\omega_p = \hbar\omega_s + \hbar\omega_i, \quad (2)$$

where ω_p , ω_s , and ω_i are the angular frequencies of the pump, signal, and idler photons, respectively.

- **Momentum Conservation (Phase Matching):**

$$\mathbf{k}_p = \mathbf{k}_s + \mathbf{k}_i, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{k}_p$, $\mathbf{k}_s$, and $\mathbf{k}_i$ are their respective wave vectors.

2.2 Phase-Matching Conditions

Phase matching is critical for optimizing the efficiency of SPDC. It ensures that the nonlinear interaction remains coherent over the crystal length. This condition is achieved when the momentum mismatch $\Delta\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{k}_p - \mathbf{k}_s - \mathbf{k}_i$ is minimized. In birefringent crystals like potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) and beta barium borate (BBO), the refractive indices for ordinary and extraordinary waves can be tailored by aligning the crystal's optical axis relative to the pump beam. Two common phase-matching configurations are:

- **Type-I Phase Matching:** Both the signal and idler photons share the same polarization.
- **Type-II Phase Matching:** The signal and idler photons have orthogonal polarizations.

These phase-matching techniques govern the emission angles, wavelengths, and spatial distributions of the down-converted photons, leading to a characteristic cone-shaped emission pattern.

2.3 Quantum Mechanical Description

SPDC is intrinsically quantum mechanical, requiring the quantization of the electromagnetic field. The process is described by the interaction Hamiltonian:

$$H_{\text{SPDC}} = i\hbar\kappa \left(\hat{a}_p \hat{a}_s^\dagger \hat{a}_i^\dagger - \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_s \hat{a}_i \right), \quad (4)$$

where κ is the coupling constant, and $\hat{a}_p$, $\hat{a}_s^\dagger$, and $\hat{a}_i^\dagger$ are the annihilation and creation operators for the pump, signal, and idler photons, respectively. The resulting quantum state of the emitted photons is a two-mode squeezed vacuum state:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sqrt{1-|q|^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^n |n\rangle_s |n\rangle_i, \quad (5)$$

where $|n\rangle_s$ and $|n\rangle_i$ denote the photon number states for the signal and idler modes, and q is a parameter proportional to the pump intensity and $\chi^{(2)}$.

3 Experimental Setup

While SPDC is a powerful tool for generating entangled photons, its efficiency is inherently low, typically on the order of 10^{-8} to 10^{-12} . Overcoming this limitation requires innovations such as quasi-phase-matched crystals, engineered waveguides, and resonant enhancement techniques. The use of integrated photonic circuits to incorporate SPDC sources into compact and scalable platforms is a promising direction for practical quantum technologies.

SPDC's ability to generate correlated and entangled photon pairs has profound implications for quantum mechanics and technology. It underpins critical advancements in quantum key distribution, quantum metrology, and fundamental tests of quantum mechanics, such as violations of Bell inequalities. Additionally, SPDC-generated photons are essential for quantum-enhanced imaging, spectroscopy, and teleportation protocols, cementing its role as a versatile and indispensable resource in quantum optics. Inspired by³², the structure is introduced for the implementation of the S.P.D.C process, which will later have the potential to be developed into a source of squeezed light production. The overall arrangement of this setup is according to figure 1a. We have built this experimental setup in the Photonics Research Laboratory for the first time at the Amirkabir University of Technology.

Figure 1. As can be seen in (a) the schematic of the setup is shown and, (b) is the real optical setup for SPDC experiment. The blue laser acts as input to the KDP crystal and the output is focused on the photodetector.

In this structure, coherent light with an input wavelength of $\lambda = 450\text{nm}$ in the visible region is passed through a nonlinear crystal of Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate (KDP) which was grown by our team at the Amirkabir University of Technology. A small portion of the beam's photons undergoes the phenomenon of "Spontaneous Parametric Down-Conversion" or S.P.D.C, converting into infrared photon couples with a wavelength of $\lambda = 900\text{nm}$. This down-converted beam which has quite weak

power due to the random nature of the SPDC process, is detected by a BPX65 PIN diode. The weak beam induces a weak current, so it needs to be further amplified, which is done by an OPA320 transimpedance to a much easier-to-detect voltage. The voltage signal then could be caught and displayed, using an Oscilloscope, or better, a Spectrum Analyzer. According to³², in a future step, by adding some sections, there will also be the possibility of producing squeezed states of light. Now we will introduce the components that were used to realize this arrangement in the Photonics Research Laboratory of Amirkabir University.

3.1 Laser Source

The laser used in this experiment is a 450 nm blue diode laser with an output power of 1 watt. This choice of laser is motivated by its high optical power and relatively compact and cost-effective design, making it suitable for generating sufficient photon flux to drive the nonlinear interaction in the potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) crystal. The wavelength of 450 nm lies in the visible spectrum, which is beneficial for aligning the experimental setup visually and ensuring precise focus into the nonlinear crystal.

The high power of the laser ensures that enough pump photons are available for the spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) process, despite the inherently low conversion efficiency of the phenomenon. Furthermore, the diode laser's compact form factor and stable output make it particularly suitable for laboratory environments with limited space.

To maintain stable operation and wavelength precision, the laser is equipped with an active cooling system. Heat dissipation is a critical aspect of high-power lasers, as temperature fluctuations can cause drift in the output wavelength and beam quality. A thermoelectric cooler (TEC) integrated within the laser module regulates its temperature, ensuring consistent performance. Additionally, the beam profile of the laser, which is approximately Gaussian (TEM₀₀ mode), provides a well-defined and highly focused beam that is ideal for coupling into the nonlinear crystal.

Alignment of the laser beam into the crystal requires precise control over the angle of incidence and the focal point. This is achieved using adjustable mirrors and a set of focusing lenses with anti-reflective coatings to minimize optical losses. The lenses are chosen to have a focal length optimized for achieving a tightly focused spot size within the crystal, which enhances the interaction efficiency between the pump photons and the nonlinear medium.

The laser stability in terms of both power and wavelength is critical for reproducibility and reliability of the SPDC process. To ensure this, the laser is operated under controlled laboratory conditions, minimizing environmental perturbations such as vibrations or air currents. Power stabilization is achieved by an integrated feedback loop within the laser driver, which continuously monitors and adjusts the current to maintain a constant output.

The choice of 450 nm as the pump wavelength is particularly advantageous for SPDC in KDP crystals. Due to the phase-matching conditions of KDP, this wavelength allows for efficient down-conversion into infrared photon pairs at approximately 900 nm. The phase-matching angle and crystal orientation are carefully tuned to maximize the overlap between the pump laser's spectral profile and the crystal's phase-matching bandwidth.

In summary, the 450 nm, 1-watt laser serves as a robust and efficient pump source for the SPDC experiment, combining high power, stability, and precise control to facilitate optimal interaction with the nonlinear medium. The system's design and careful integration ensure that it meets the demanding requirements of quantum optical experiments while remaining accessible and cost-effective.

3.2 Nonlinear Crystal: Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate (KDP)

The nonlinear crystal used in this experiment as shown in Figure 2 is potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP), a widely recognized material for its excellent nonlinear optical properties and versatility in applications such as harmonic generation and parametric down-conversion. KDP crystals are particularly advantageous for spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) due to their high transparency in the ultraviolet to infrared spectrum, strong second-order nonlinear susceptibility ($\chi^{(2)}$), and relatively low cost compared to alternative nonlinear crystals.

Figure 2. The nonlinear KDP crystal grown in the Photonics Research Laboratory of Amirkabir University, is seen in its holder right after the laser in the setup

3.2.1 Crystal Growth and Preparation

The KDP crystal used in this setup was grown in-house at the Photonics Research Laboratory at Amirkabir University of Technology. The growth process began with the preparation of a saturated solution, where 99.5% pure KDP powder was dissolved in 500 milliliters of distilled water at a temperature of 70–80°C. The solution was stirred continuously using a magnetic stirrer until the solute fully dissolved. After filtration through grade 42 ashless filter paper, the solution was placed in a sealed chamber, protected from light, to facilitate crystal growth.

Seed crystals formed naturally in the solution during the initial cooling period. These were carefully selected, cleaned, and suspended in the saturated solution to act as nucleation sites for further growth. Over several weeks, a single high-quality crystal was grown by maintaining a stable temperature and controlling the evaporation rate of the solvent. The process was repeated to refine the crystal's optical properties, ensuring minimal defects and high optical clarity. The final crystal, with dimensions optimized for phase-matching and beam propagation, is depicted in Figure ??.

3.2.2 Nonlinear Optical Properties

KDP is a birefringent crystal, meaning its refractive index depends on the polarization and propagation direction of the incident light. This property is critical for phase-matching, a condition that ensures the conservation of momentum in the SPDC process. The refractive indices for ordinary and extraordinary polarizations can be precisely tuned by orienting the crystal's optical axis at the appropriate angle relative to the pump beam.

For this experiment, a type-I phase-matching configuration was employed, where the signal and idler photons share the same polarization, which is orthogonal to the pump beam's polarization. By adjusting the phase-matching angle of the crystal, efficient conversion of the 450 nm pump photons into signal and idler photons at approximately 900 nm was achieved. The high transparency of KDP in the visible and near-infrared regions further enhances the efficiency of SPDC by minimizing absorption losses.

3.2.3 Crystal Alignment and Handling

Proper alignment of the KDP crystal is critical to achieving optimal phase-matching conditions. The crystal was mounted on a high-precision goniometer stage that allowed for fine adjustments in three rotational degrees of freedom. The pump laser beam was carefully aligned to propagate along the crystal's principal axis, ensuring maximum overlap with the phase-matching region. Anti-reflective coatings were applied to the crystal surfaces to reduce Fresnel losses and prevent back-reflections that could destabilize the laser source.

Temperature stabilization of the crystal was also implemented to maintain consistent refractive indices, as thermal fluctuations can shift the phase-matching conditions. The crystal was enclosed in a thermally controlled housing to minimize environmental influences, ensuring long-term stability and reproducibility of the experiment.

3.2.4 Advantages and Challenges

KDP's combination of high damage threshold, wide transparency range, and excellent nonlinear properties makes it an ideal choice for this SPDC experiment. However, its relatively low nonlinear coefficient compared to some alternatives, such as beta

barium borate (BBO), poses challenges in terms of conversion efficiency. To address this limitation, a high-intensity pump laser and precise alignment techniques were employed.

In future iterations, additional enhancements such as quasi-phase-matched KDP crystals or temperature-tuned phase matching could be explored to further optimize efficiency. The integration of advanced anti-reflective coatings or waveguide structures could also improve the coupling efficiency and output quality.

The KDP crystal plays a pivotal role in the SPDC process by enabling the conversion of pump photons into entangled photon pairs. Its excellent optical properties, combined with careful growth, preparation, and alignment, make it a robust and versatile nonlinear medium for quantum optics experiments. This detailed understanding of its properties and behavior ensures that the experiment achieves the desired outcomes with high reliability.

3.3 Detector: BPX65 Photodiode

The BPX65 silicon PIN photodiode as depicted in Figure 3 is employed as the primary detection element in this experiment to measure the weak optical signal generated by the spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) process. This detector is specifically chosen for its high sensitivity, fast response time, and compatibility with the wavelength range of the generated photon pairs. These characteristics make the BPX65 a reliable and efficient choice for detecting infrared photons at 900 nm.

3.3.1 Key Specifications and Features

The BPX65 photodiode, manufactured by Centronic, is a silicon-based PIN detector with the following critical specifications:

- **Active Area:** 1 mm², providing a sufficient detection surface while maintaining high speed.
- **Spectral Responsivity:** Peaks at approximately 900nm, making it ideal for detecting the down-converted photons generated in this experiment.
- **Dark Current:** As low as 1 nA, ensuring minimal noise even in low-light conditions.
- **Operating Temperature Range:** -40°C to +125°C, enabling operation in a wide range of environmental conditions.
- **Reverse Bias Voltage:** 0 to 20 V, which can be adjusted to optimize the responsivity and reduce junction capacitance for faster response times.

The BPX65 is highly responsive at the 900nm wavelength of the signal and idler photons, with a typical responsivity of 0.51 A/W at this wavelength. This high responsivity ensures efficient conversion of incident photons into an electrical signal, which is crucial given the low power of the down-converted beam.

3.3.2 Operation and Signal Detection

To maximize detection efficiency, the BPX65 photodiode is reverse-biased. This configuration reduces the junction capacitance, increasing the detector's bandwidth and response speed. The reverse bias also improves the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) by minimizing the influence of the diode's inherent noise, such as dark current.

The detected signal is extremely weak, as the SPDC process typically produces photon pairs with power levels in the picowatt range. To address this, the output current of the photodiode is fed into a transimpedance amplifier (OPA320) that converts the small current into a measurable voltage signal. The amplifier's low-noise characteristics are critical for preserving the integrity of the weak signal.

Figure 3. PIN diode photodetector. This detector is the same detector that had been used in a similar experiment in 1988³²

3.3.3 Thermal Noise Reduction

Thermal noise, primarily arising from the dark current of the detector, poses a significant challenge in low-light detection scenarios. To mitigate this, the BPX65 photodiode is integrated into a thermally regulated system. A Peltier cooling element reduces the detector's temperature to approximately -40°C , significantly lowering the dark current and associated noise. This allows the detector to operate with higher sensitivity and improved accuracy.

The thermal regulation system includes a water-cooled heatsink to dissipate excess heat from the Peltier element, maintaining stable cooling performance. This combination of active cooling and thermal management ensures optimal detector operation even in long-duration experiments.

3.3.4 Infrared Filtering

An infrared (IR) filter is placed in front of the photodiode to ensure that only photons at the desired 900 nm wavelength are detected. The filter blocks visible and ultraviolet light, eliminating background noise from stray or scattered pump photons and ensuring that the signal originates solely from the down-converted photons. This significantly improves the experiment's overall accuracy and reliability.

3.3.5 Alignment and Positioning

The BPX65 detector is mounted on an adjustable stage to allow precise alignment with the optical axis of the SPDC beam. Lenses are used to focus the diverging down-converted photons onto the active area of the photodiode, maximizing photon collection efficiency. The alignment is fine-tuned to ensure that the signal beam fully overlaps the sensitive area of the detector.

3.3.6 Advantages and Challenges

The BPX65 offers an excellent balance between sensitivity, speed, and affordability. Its ability (see figure 4) to operate over a wide range of temperatures and its high spectral responsivity make it an ideal choice for SPDC experiments. However, its limited active area requires precise alignment, and its noise performance, while sufficient for most applications, could be further improved by using avalanche photodiodes (APDs) in future iterations.

The BPX65 photodiode serves as a critical component in the SPDC experimental setup, converting weak optical signals into measurable electrical outputs with high efficiency. Its integration with cooling systems, filtering mechanisms, and precision alignment ensures reliable detection of down-converted photons, enabling the accurate measurement and analysis of the SPDC process. Future improvements may focus on advanced photodetector technologies and enhanced signal processing to further optimize detection capabilities.

(a) Dark current vs reverse voltage changes

(b) Dark current vs temperature changes (reverse voltage is 20volts)

(c) Relative Spectral Response of BPX65

Figure 4. These figures are showing characteristics of (a) Dark Current of our silicon photodiode BPX65 in terms of the reverse voltage and, (b) depicts its dark current versus its temperature as we decrease its temperature into -40 celcius to lower its dark current in our experiment and (c) shows its spectral respose which proves that it is sensitive enough around 900nm which aligns with our experiment.³³

3.4 Amplification: OPA320 Operational Amplifier

To process the weak electrical signals generated by the BPX65 photodiode, the OPA320 operational amplifier is employed as a transimpedance amplifier in the experimental setup. This device is crucial for converting the minute current output from the

photodiode into a measurable voltage signal with minimal noise and distortion. The OPA320 is chosen for its high precision, low noise, and fast response, making it ideal for handling the low-power signals generated in the spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) process.

3.4.1 Key Specifications and Features

The Texas Instruments OPA320 is a high-performance, low-noise CMOS operational amplifier with the following critical specifications:

- **Bandwidth:** 20MHz, enabling high-speed signal processing.
- **Input Bias Current:** 0.9pA, minimizing signal distortion and preserving the integrity of weak input currents.
- **Noise Density:** 7nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at 10kHz, ensuring low-noise operation.
- **Offset Voltage:** 150 μV , providing high accuracy with minimal offset error.
- **Common-Mode Rejection Ratio (CMRR):** 114dB, which enhances stability by suppressing noise from common-mode signals.
- **Supply Voltage Range:** 1.8V to 5.5V, allowing for flexible power supply options.
- **Slew Rate:** 10V/ μs , enabling rapid response to transient signal changes.

These features make the OPA320 particularly suited for applications demanding high precision and low noise, such as detecting the weak photon-pair signals from the SPDC process.

3.4.2 Transimpedance Amplification

The primary function of the OPA320 in this setup is to act as a transimpedance amplifier, converting the small current output from the BPX65 photodiode into a proportional voltage. The transimpedance configuration employs a feedback resistor to determine the amplification factor, with the resulting output voltage given by:

$$V_{\text{out}} = -I_{\text{in}}R_f, \quad (6)$$

where I_{in} is the photodiode current and R_f is the feedback resistor. A high-value feedback resistor is selected to amplify the weak photodiode currents, which are typically in the nanoampere range, into detectable voltage levels suitable for measurement by oscilloscopes or spectrum analyzers.

3.4.3 Noise Reduction and Stability

Minimizing noise is critical for the accurate detection of SPDC signals. The OPA320's low input bias current and noise density ensure that the inherent noise from the amplifier does not mask the weak signal from the photodiode. Additionally, the high CMRR prevents interference from common-mode noise sources, such as power supply fluctuations or environmental electromagnetic interference.

To enhance stability and further reduce noise, a capacitor is placed in parallel with the feedback resistor to limit the amplifier's bandwidth to the signal of interest. This configuration acts as a low-pass filter, effectively suppressing high-frequency noise while preserving the integrity of the SPDC signal.

3.4.4 Thermal Management

Operating the amplifier at a stable temperature is essential for maintaining consistent performance. While the OPA320 is inherently low-power and generates minimal heat, the entire amplification circuit is placed in a thermally regulated environment to ensure that external temperature fluctuations do not affect the signal gain or introduce drift in the output.

3.4.5 PCB Design and Implementation

The OPA320 is integrated into a custom-designed printed circuit board (PCB) that minimizes parasitic capacitance and inductance. The PCB layout ensures short feedback loops and robust grounding to reduce noise and improve signal fidelity. The amplifier circuit includes test points for monitoring the signal at various stages, facilitating troubleshooting and calibration.

3.4.6 Advantages and Challenges

The OPA320 offers a powerful combination of precision, low noise, and high-speed performance, making it an excellent choice for SPDC detection. However, achieving optimal performance requires careful circuit design, including proper selection of the feedback resistor and capacitor, as well as shielding to prevent external noise interference. Future improvements could explore advanced amplifier designs with even lower noise characteristics or integrated photodiode-amplifier modules for enhanced compactness.

The OPA320 operational amplifier is a critical component of the SPDC experimental setup, enabling the detection of weak optical signals with high sensitivity and precision. Its low-noise, high-gain properties ensure that the electrical signal from the photodiode is amplified to measurable levels without significant distortion. By combining advanced circuit design with thermal and noise management, the amplifier plays a pivotal role in the success of the SPDC experiment.

Figure 5. This amplifier is suitable for this experiment due to its high amplifying and low noise in its inputs.³⁴

These two components are used in a circuit similar to that proposed in reference³⁵. The PCB layout of this circuit can be seen in figure 6 [5]. It is essentially a transimpedance amplifier circuit that amplifies the current of detectors to amplified voltage. The circuit design can be seen in figure 7a. And the equivalent AC circuit in figure 7b. further calculations can be seen in³⁵.

Figure 6. PCB layout of the photodiode amplifier. The top layer is shown in red and the bottom layer is shown in blue

Figure 7. The circuit of the photodetector sensor.

Figure 8. Infrared filter with radius 1cm. we put this infrared filter not to pass blue light so the detection of the PIN diode becomes just the photon pairs that generated.

3.5 Cooling System: Peltier Module, Water Cooling, and Heatsink

Effective thermal management is crucial in the experimental setup to reduce noise in the detection system, particularly the dark current of the BPX65 photodiode. The cooling system implemented in this experiment combines a thermoelectric cooling element (Peltier module), a water cooling system, and a heatsink to achieve stable and low operating temperatures for the detector.

3.5.1 Thermoelectric Cooling (Peltier Module)

The primary cooling component is an 8 cm × 8 cm Peltier module. This thermoelectric cooler operates on the Peltier effect, where an electric current drives heat transfer between two ceramic plates. By applying a voltage across the module, heat is absorbed from the cold side and dissipated through the hot side, resulting in a significant temperature drop on the cold side.

In this setup, the Peltier module is directly attached to the photodiode housing, reducing the temperature of the BPX65 photodiode to approximately -40°C . This low temperature dramatically reduces the dark current of the photodiode, thereby minimizing thermal noise and enhancing the sensitivity of the detection system. A 12 V, 20 A power supply is used to drive the Peltier module, ensuring consistent cooling performance even under prolonged operation.

3.5.2 Water Cooling System

To maintain the efficiency of the Peltier module, effective heat dissipation from its hot side is essential. A water cooling system is employed for this purpose, consisting of a water block, a pump, and a radiator. The water block is mounted on the hot side of the Peltier module, allowing heat to be transferred into a circulating coolant.

The water pump ensures a continuous flow of coolant through the water block and radiator, where the heat is dissipated into the surrounding environment. The radiator, equipped with high-efficiency fans, enhances the heat transfer process, preventing thermal saturation of the Peltier module and maintaining its cooling capacity. This active cooling design ensures that the temperature gradient across the Peltier module remains optimal, enabling consistent performance.

3.5.3 Heatsink for Thermal Stabilization

In addition to water cooling, a heatsink is used to further enhance the dissipation of heat from the Peltier module's hot side. The heatsink is constructed from aluminum, chosen for its high thermal conductivity and lightweight properties. The fins of the

heatsink are designed to maximize surface area, allowing for efficient heat transfer to the surrounding air.

The combination of the heatsink and water cooling system ensures that the Peltier module operates within its safe thermal limits, preventing overheating and potential damage. This dual-layer approach to heat dissipation provides redundancy and enhances the reliability of the cooling system.

3.5.4 Integration and Operation

The entire cooling system, including the Peltier module (see 9a), water block, pump, radiator, and heatsink, is integrated into a compact and thermally stable enclosure. The photodiode and amplifier circuits are placed within this cooled environment to ensure consistent operation and minimal thermal noise.

To monitor and control the system's performance, temperature sensors are installed at critical points, including the cold side of the Peltier module, the photodiode housing, and the coolant flow. These sensors provide real-time feedback to ensure that the cooling system maintains the desired operating conditions.

The cooling system's operation is designed to be user-friendly and robust, with the water pump and radiator fans powered by the same 12 V power supply as shown in figure 10 as the Peltier module. This integrated power setup simplifies the system and ensures synchronized operation of all cooling components.

3.5.5 Advantages and Challenges

The Peltier-based cooling system offers several advantages:

- **Reduced Dark Current:** By lowering the photodiode temperature to -40°C , the dark current is significantly reduced, improving the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the detection system.
- **Stable Operation:** The combination of water cooling and a heatsink prevents thermal saturation, enabling stable long-term operation.
- **Compact Design:** The system's compact integration makes it suitable for laboratory environments with limited space.

However, the system also presents challenges:

- **Condensation Risk:** Operating at low temperatures can lead to condensation on the cooled surfaces, potentially damaging electronic components. This issue is mitigated by enclosing the system in a sealed and desiccated chamber.
- **Power Consumption:** The Peltier module and cooling components require significant power, necessitating a high-capacity power supply.
- **Complexity:** The addition of multiple cooling components increases the setup's complexity and requires careful maintenance to ensure proper operation.

Consequently, the cooling system is a vital component of the SPDC experimental setup, enabling the photodiode to operate at low temperatures for enhanced sensitivity. By combining a Peltier module, water cooling, and a heatsink, the system effectively manages heat dissipation and ensures stable performance. This robust design minimizes thermal noise and maximizes the efficiency of the detection system, contributing significantly to the success of the experiment.

(a) Thermoelectric cooling element

(b) Water block to cool down the Peltier

Figure 9. (a) peltier to cool down the detector into -40 celcius to reduce the dark current, (b) water block beside the peltier and heatsink to ake sure peltier or thermoelectric cooling element works properly at -40 celcius

Figure 10. The front view and ports of the 12 – volt and 20 – amp power supply. The ports, from left to right, are as follows: 110 or 220 – volt city power phase, city power neutral, earth wire connection, three ground output ports (negative terminal), three voltage output ports (positive terminal), and one screw for precise output voltage adjustment

4 Results and Conclusion

4.1 Results

The experimental setup developed at the Photonics Research Laboratory successfully demonstrated the feasibility of generating and detecting photon pairs through the spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) process. Using a 450 nm, 1-watt blue diode laser as the pump source and a self-grown potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) nonlinear crystal, we achieved the conversion of pump photons into correlated photon pairs at approximately 900 nm.

The generated photon pairs were detected using a BPX65 PIN photodiode integrated with a custom-designed transimpedance amplifier circuit based on the OPA320 operational amplifier. The weak optical signals generated by the SPDC process, typically on the order of 10 picowatts, were amplified to measurable voltage levels in the range of 2 to 3 millivolts, as observed on an oscilloscope. This level of amplification aligns well with theoretical predictions, confirming the validity of the experimental setup.

Temperature control of the BPX65 photodiode, achieved using a Peltier cooling module combined with water cooling and a heatsink, significantly reduced thermal noise, improving the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The dark current was reduced to negligible levels at a photodiode operating temperature of -40°C . The use of an infrared filter further ensured that only the down-converted photons were detected, eliminating background noise from the pump laser and ambient light.

The observed results confirm the theoretical foundations of SPDC, including energy and momentum conservation in the nonlinear interaction. The phase-matching conditions were optimized to ensure efficient down-conversion, resulting in a characteristic cone-shaped emission of photon pairs from the KDP crystal. The measured signals showed strong agreement with theoretical predictions, validating the performance of the system and demonstrating its ability to operate effectively with accessible and low-cost components.

4.2 Conclusion

This study presents a robust and cost-effective implementation of an SPDC experimental setup, utilizing accessible components and self-grown nonlinear crystals. The successful detection of correlated photon pairs highlights the potential of this system as a platform for quantum optics research and education.

One of the key achievements of this work is the demonstration that high-sensitivity SPDC experiments can be conducted with minimal resources. The use of a KDP crystal grown in-house underscores the accessibility of this approach, providing an avenue for researchers and educators in resource-limited environments to engage with advanced quantum optics experiments. The integration of the BPX65 photodiode and OPA320 amplifier demonstrates the feasibility of detecting weak optical signals with low-cost, commercially available components, while the advanced cooling system ensures stable and reliable operation.

The scalability and adaptability of the setup make it a promising candidate for further advancements. Potential enhancements include the incorporation of additional optical elements, such as electro-optic modulators and feedback amplifiers, to enable the generation of squeezed states of light. These developments could open pathways to quantum-enhanced sensing, secure quantum communication, and other advanced applications in quantum technologies.

This work bridges the gap between theoretical insights and practical realization, providing a blueprint for implementing SPDC-based experiments in diverse settings. By demonstrating the accessibility and scalability of SPDC systems, this study aims to inspire further exploration and innovation in the field of nonlinear optics and quantum technologies. Future directions include optimizing the system for higher conversion efficiencies, integrating photonic waveguides, and exploring novel nonlinear materials to enhance performance.

In conclusion, the results of this study emphasize the transformative potential of SPDC as a tool for foundational research and technological development. By making advanced quantum optics experiments more accessible, this work contributes to the growing efforts to democratize quantum technologies and expand their impact across scientific disciplines and industries.

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Additional information

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